

Solvent Effect on the Electronic Spectral Characteristics of Neutral Red

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Neutral red has been used extensively as a probe in biological systems¹. In spite of its wide biologically important applications, little attention has been paid to its spectral properties. Rao and Narayana² investigated the aggregation behaviour of neutral red by spectral measurements while Bartels³ examined the spectral behaviour of neutral red as a function of a_H . The present work is devoted to the investigation of the effect of organic solvents on the electronic spectral behaviour of neutral red, in order to clarify the effect of solvent and neutral red concentration on the nature of the absorbing species liable to exist.

Results and Discussion

Effect on neutral red concentration: The visible electronic spectra of different concentrations of neutral red (HIN^+) in various organic solvents, methanol, ethanol, dimethylformamide (DMF), acetonitrile (AN) and carbon tetrachloride have been recorded in the wavelength range 380–680 nm. Representative results are shown in Figs. 1–3, which indicate that the visible electronic spectra of neutral red are largely dependent on its concentration as well as on the nature of the organic solvent employed.

Generally, the recorded visible spectra of low concentrations of neutral red in the basic solvents methanol ($\leq 2.0 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm⁻³), ethanol ($\leq 7.5 \times 10^{-6}$ mol dm⁻³) and DMF ($\leq 1.5 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³) show mainly one absorption band located in the wavelength range 455–468 nm (Figs. 1, 2 and Table 1). On increasing the HIN^+ concentration beyond the above mentioned limit for each solvent, a second new band develops at longer wavelength (527–543 nm). In the case of methanol and ethanol, the main shorter wavelength band gradually disappears whereas at high HIN^+ concentrations ($\geq 8 \times 10^{-5}$ and 4×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ respectively) it appears as an ill-defined shoulder (Fig. 1). On the other hand, in DMF, the absorbance of the main shorter wavelength band increases by increasing the HIN^+ concentration (Fig. 2). This behaviour can be interpreted on the principle that in dilute solutions, this compound (HIN^+) is liable to exist in the neutral deprotonated form (IN) leucobase under the basicity effect of the organic solvent,

Accordingly, the main visible absorption band appearing in dilute solutions of these solvents (deep yellow or orange) can be ascribed to absorption of the neutral form (IN). With increasing compound concentration, the possibility of formation of the (IN) form is lowered, where beyond a certain concentration limit as explained above the compound exists mostly in the charge protonated form (HIN^+). Thus the observed absorption in the spectra of concentrated neutral red solutions (pink colour) can be ascribed to absorption of the neutral red protonated form.

Fig. 1. Electronic absorption spectra of different concentrations of neutral red in methanol: (a) 0.5, (b) 1.0, (c) 1.5, (d) 2.0, (e) 2.5, (f) 3.0, (g) 3.5, (h) 4.0, (i) 4.5, (j) 5.0, (k) 6.0, (m) 7.0, and (n) 8.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³.

Fig. 2. Electronic absorption spectra of different concentrations of neutral red in DMF: (a) 0.20, (b) 0.50, (c) 0.70, (d) 1.00, (e) 1.25, (f) 1.50, (g) 1.75, (h) 2.00, (i) 2.25, (j) 2.50, (k) 2.75 and (m) 3.00×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³.

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF NEUTRAL (IN) AND PROTONATED (HIN⁺) FORMS OF NEUTRAL RED IN VARIOUS SOLVENTS

Solvent	IN		HIN ⁺	
	λ_{\max} (nm)	ϵ_{\max} mol ⁻¹ dm ⁻³ cm ⁻¹	λ_{\max} (nm)	ϵ_{\max} mol ⁻¹ dm ⁻³ cm ⁻¹
Methanol	468	21 600	538	25 500
Ethanol	469	18 800	540	32 000
DMF	455	21 429	543	7 178
Acetonitrile	—	—	536	12 875
CCl ₄	—	—	535	34 000

Generally, the lower concentration limit of neutral red at which it exists mostly in the protonated form decreases on changing the basic organic solvent from methanol to ethanol (2.0×10^{-6} and 7.5×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³) respectively. This trend is in accordance with the expected decreasing in solvent basicity in the same direction ($pK_a^{250} = 16.7$ and 18.9 mol dm⁻³)² respectively⁴. This reflects itself in a strong hydrogen bond donation from neutral red to the solvent in the same direction.

Fig. 3. Electronic absorption spectra of different concentrations of neutral red in acetonitrile: (a) 1.0, (b) 2.0, (c) 4.0, (d) 6.0, (e) 8.0, (f) 10.0, (g) 12.0, (h) 14.0 and (i) 15.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³.

In terms of basicity effect, the unexpected high concentration limit at which neutral red starts to appear as protonated form HIN⁺ in DMF (1.5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³) as compared to that in methanol ($pK_a^{250} = 18$ and 16.7 (mol dm⁻³)² respectively)⁴ can be ascribed to the pronounced character of DMF as a strong hydrogen bond acceptor. This facilitates the deprotonation process of HIN⁺.

Convincing evidence for the presence of neutral red, in its dilute solutions of the basic organic solvents, in an acid-base equilibria, is achieved from recording the visible spectra of acid and alkaline methanol, ethanol and DMF neutral red solutions. It is observed that the spectra are characterised by absorption bands located at more or less the same wavelengths as those reported for the corresponding media in the presence of high and low neutral red concentrations. Moreover, this interpretation can be supported by the reported pK_a values for neutral red (6.5)⁵.

Further convincing evidence for the presence of neutral red in basic solvents in an acid-base equilibrium of the type, $HIN^+ \rightleftharpoons IN + H^+$, is obtained from studying the visible spectra of 5×10^{-5} and 2×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ concentrations of

this compound in methanol and ethanol in the temperature range 7–58° (Fig. 4). It is evident that with increase in temperature, the intensity of the orange IN band increases at the expense of the pink band. This is due to the expected easier deprotonation process of the HIN^+ form on increasing the temperature. On the other hand, the visible spectra of neutral red in the weak basic solvents acetonitrile and CCl_4 , show a main visible band at 536 and 535 nm respectively (Fig. 3). In such cases the position of the observed band is little affected by increasing the HIN^+ concentration where its λ_{max} is slightly red-shifted. The disappearance of the shorter visible band responsible for absorption of the non-protonated form (IN) even in very dilute solutions of these two solvents reveals the difficult formation of the neutral form (IN) leucobase. This behaviour is consistent with the low basicity of these solvents ($\text{p}K_s^{25^\circ}$ for AN=28.5 (mol dm^{-3})²).

band delonging to absorption of the neutral form (IN) is absent in acetonitrile. This behaviour strongly suggests that specific solute-solvent interactions, viz. basicity effect rather than electrostatic ones, play an important role in determining the acid-base properties of neutral red in organic solvents.

It is worthy to mention that the different concentrations employed in the present study lie below the lower limit at which aggregation of the dye starts to occur as reported earlier². Also, the observed λ_{max} values for the protonated and non-protonated forms are in agreement with those reported earlier².

Band assignment and solvent effect: The λ_{max} values along with the corresponding ϵ_{max} values of the visible bands of both HIN^+ and IN forms in the various solvents used are listed in Table 1. The two visible bands responsible for absorption of the

Fig. 4. Electronic absorption spectra of neutral red ($2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in ethanol at different temperatures: (a) 7°, (b) 15°, (c) 25°, (d) 38°, (e) 50° and (f) 58°.

Examination of Table 1 reveals that though acetonitrile and methanol have the same dielectric constant (36.0 and 32.6 respectively) the spectral behaviour of neutral red in these solvents are quite different (Figs. 1 and 3). The shorter visible

neutral and protonated forms (IN) and (HIN^+) respectively, can be assigned to a transition involving the whole species associated with intramolecular charge transfer. This charge transfer seems to originate from the $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ group as a source

Fig. 5. Electronic absorption spectra of 2.0×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} of neutral red in DMF-acetonitrile (AN) mixtures (v/v): (a) 0.0, (b) 10, (c) 30, (d) 50, (e) 60, (f) 65, (g) 70, (h) 75, (i) 80, (j) 90 and (k) 100% AN.

to the N-H phenazonium cation as a sink in the case of the HIN^+ form. The CT take place within the HIN^+ can be represented schematically as

It is expected that the CT interaction liable to occur in the HIN^+ form, is easier in comparison to that taking place in the neutral one. This reflects itself in a lower excitation energy for the CT band of the HIN^+ form relative to that of the IN form. However, this is the case observed as it is evident from the results displayed in Table 1. Generally, it was found that the intramolecular CT band

is characterised by low excitation energy in amphiprotic solvents (MeOH and EtOH) relative to that in dipolar aprotic ones DMF (Figs. 1 and 2, Table 1). This is presumably due to the specific hydrogen bonding interaction of the amphiprotic solvent with nitrogen phenazonium ring of the IN form resulting in a high electron-accepting power of phenazine ring, i.e. easier charge delocalisation. On the other hand, λ_{max} of the protonated form acquires a little red shift as the polarity of the organic solvent is increased ($\text{CCl}_4 \rightarrow \text{acetonitrile} \rightarrow \text{methanol} \rightarrow \text{ethanol} \rightarrow \text{DMF}$). This shift can be explained on the basis that the excited state of this transition being more polar as explained above. Therefore it is better stabilised by polar solvents through dipole-dipole interactions.

Spectra in mixed organic solvents: This study was preformed in order to confirm the existence of neutral red in its dilute solution in an acid-base equilibrium as a result of the basicity of the organic solvent. Therefore the visible spectra of neutral red in the high basicity DMF solvent containing successively increasing amounts of weak basic solvent, viz. acetonitrile, have been investigated (Fig. 5). It is evident that with increasing acetonitrile concentration in neutral red DMF medium the intensity of the main visible band belonging to absorption of IN form gradually decreases and meanwhile a new band is developed at longer wavelength, i.e. the protonated form HIN^+ starts to appear as the basicity of the medium is lowered. The spectra (Fig. 5) show an isosbestic point around 476 nm suggesting the existence of neutral red in acid-base equilibrium in such media.

Experimental

Neutral red used was of AnalaR grade. All solvents used were of spectral grade (B.D.H. or Merck). Stock solutions (10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}) of the compound were prepared in the appropriate volume of each solvent, and dilute solutions were obtained by dilution with the proper solvent. The electronic spectra were recorded on a Cecil CE 599 spectrophotometer using 1-cm matched cell. The spectrophotometer was fitted with temperature control unit. The measured solution temperature could be controlled within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ using a Haake Ultrathermostat.

References

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